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Motivational Teaching Strategies in Mathematics in the New Normal

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Abstract

This study focused on the motivational teaching strategies in Mathematics in the new normal in Jimmy Carter Middle School, Albuquerque Public Schools, during the school year 2021-2022 to improve the learners' performance. It looked into the mathematics teachers' profile, the learners' performance level during the first quarter, the significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and their performance in Mathematics, and learners' attitudes toward studying Mathematics. The researcher found that most mathematics teachers are educationally qualified, have minimum teaching experience, and have attended various seminars about mathematics. The learners obtained a very satisfactory performance. The profile of the teachers is significantly related to the level of performance of the learners in Mathematics. The attitude of the learners towards Mathematics, along with school-related factors such as Study habits and Peers Family – family-related factors like Parents and Siblings, and Teacher-related factors are the factors affecting the learners' performance. The proposed motivational strategies could improve the attitude and performance of learners towards Mathematics. The researcher recommended that the proposed motivational strategies be presented to the Superintendent for their reproduction and utilization to help the mathematics teachers. Teachers should make instructional materials to improve the performance of the pupils. Such interventions/materials help them understand more clearly the concepts. Parents and teachers should join hands in improving the performance of the learners. Teachers should tell the parents about their children's difficulties in learning Mathematics. Parents should also monitor the performance of their children in the school. They should give their full support in their studies, like attending PTA meetings and having follow-ups in their studies. The skills that are least learned in mathematics should be emphasized in teaching. Teachers should use appropriate strategies and techniques to develop the skills and give more exercise for the students to master the skills.

Keywords: *motivational, teaching, strategies, mathematics, new normal*

Introduction

In this world of modern technology, no nation can attain a meaningful stage of economic development without availing itself of the advances made in science. However, its advance in science is minimized if its people are not receptive to mathematics. It is in the context of the foregoing propositions that educational institutions with the support of the government promote the study of Mathematics so that this country can keep pace with progress.

The world is interconnected. Everyday math shows these connections and possibilities. The earlier young learners can put skills to practice, the more likely our country will remain an innovative society progressive.

Mathematics with its abstract symbolism, its logical structures and its wide application has a unique importance. There is no doubt that it is an important subject in the sense that mathematical skills are important tools in solving a variety of problems which one encounters in his daily life. It is a fact that mathematics plays an important role in liberal education and, consequently, in man's life, because it is needed in practically all field of knowledge. Mathematics, so remarkable and important subject, should therefore be taught as effectively as possible.

Thus, if we were to be exact, we must know our subject matter well before teaching knowledge, skills and concepts. And this is the best answer to the problem that learners perform low in their class. Teachers teaching Mathematics in the elementary level must be knowledgeable and must have a wide understanding of the development of the different mathematical skills.

Today, the teaching of mathematics is one of the most disliked subjects because some teachers cannot understand and appreciate the value of numbers. Sometimes it may lead to the downfall of the Mathematics program due to the shortcomings of teachers teaching Mathematics skills. Thus, if our learners were to play an intelligent part in the activities of the world around us, they must be able to interpret and use mathematical skills, concepts and relationships.

Algebra can explain how quickly water becomes contaminated and how many people in a third world country drinking that water might become sick on a yearly basis. A study of geometry can explain the science behind architecture throughout the world. Statistics and probability can estimate death tolls from earthquakes, conflicts and other calamities around the world. It can also predict profits, how ideas spread and how previously endangered animals might repopulate. Math is a powerful tool for global understanding and communication. Using it, students can make sense of the world and solve complex and real problems. Rethinking math in a global context offers students a twist on the typical content that makes the math itself more applicable and meaningful for students. (http://asiasociety.org/education/resources-schools/professional-learning/understanding-world_through-math).

Mathematics is around us. It is present in different forms. Right from getting up in early hours of the day to the ringing of an alarm,

reading time on a watch, rounding a date on a calendar, picking up the phone, preparing a recipe in the kitchen, to wait for the counts of whistles of the cooker, managing money, traveling to some places, to exchanging currency at a ticket outlet while availing oneself of a public conveyance or checking up the mileage of your car, halting at the filing station, attending to a roll call at school, getting scores in the class exams, even meeting new friends, the list is just endless if one goes on to note down the situations when our computational skill, or more specifically simple mathematics comes to play a role; almost every next moment we do the simple calculations at the back of our mind.

The Mathematics teacher plays an important role in providing the learners a conducive learning environment. The goal of all educational reforms must be directed towards the learning of students under the K – 12 curriculum as implemented by the Department of Education. This program and project by the DepEd must all center on making learners learn how to compute difficult problems in the teaching and developing of mathematical skills.

In the Philippines, the mission of the Department of Education is to protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture – based, and complete basic education where students learn in a child – friendly, gender – sensitive, safe, and motivating environment; where teachers facilitate learning and constantly nurture every learner; where administrators and staff, as stewards of the institution; ensure an enabling and supportive environment for effective learning to happen; and family, community, and other stakeholders are actively engaged and share responsibility in developing life – long learners.

According to the study of Batomalaque (2009), many of our Filipino students are not attaining functional literacy, without which they find it difficult to meet the challenges posed by our rapidly changing world. The main factors which can be cited to account for the low performance in Mathematics of the Filipino students includes the lack of Mathematics culture and deficiencies regarding the school curriculum, the teaching – learning process, instructional materials and teacher training.

Based on the National Educational Testing and Research Center (NETRC) Statistical Data, the average National Achievement Test (NAT) mean percentage score (MPS) in NAT Grade 10 in all subjects of SY 2011 – 2012 is 48.90 percent distributed as follows: Mathematics 46.37; Filipino 51.27; English 51.80; Science 40.53; and Araling Panlipunan 54.22. On the Division level the overall MPS is 39.86. Based on the presented data, it could be deduced that mathematics is second to the lowest, among the tested subjects in the National Achievement Test MPS among the five subject areas.

Because of the students' low performance in the National Achievement Test, the department recommended some policies to improve the performance in the National Achievement test by coming up with remedial classes, and varied forms of assessment and maximizing the utilization of NAT Results for intervention and remedial instruction (exposition of Dr. Nelia V. Benito, DepEd NETRC on NAT overview and results, January 2012.)

On April 13, 2005, then DepEd Secretary Florencio Abad issued Memorandum No. 117 s. 2005 on the conduct of a training workshop on Strategic Intervention for successful learning. This aims to enhance teachers' skills in test analysis and interpretation and capacitate them in developing intervention materials for remediation and enrichment of learning. With this, the government and the Department of Education are stepping up in their efforts to upgrade the quality of Science and Mathematics education in the country. There are funds being allocated for the purchase of Science and Math instructional materials and devices and the conduct of teacher training. Another incentive being given to the teachers is provided by the mandate and implementation of DepEd Order No. 79, s. 2012 dated October 10, 2012 granting step increment for teachers with specialization in Science or in Mathematics to boost their teaching on these primary subjects. As propounded by Education Secretary Bro. Armin A. Luistro, "Science and Mathematics are fundamental tools of industrialization which we certainly need to strengthen our global competitiveness".

Intervention materials are designed to help teachers provide the students needed support to make progress. These tried to increase and deepen their skills, knowledge and understanding from concrete to what is more abstract. They gave the students the opportunity to explore their understanding and make sense of these new scientific ideas. They helped the students talk what they know and understand from the teacher to formalize their thinking. Furthermore, they were intervention materials meant to re-teach the concept(s) and skills(s) to help the learners master a competency – based skill which they were not able to develop from classroom teaching.

It is claimed that the Mathematics teacher needs to know the learning style preferences of the students in class and how to work effectively with them. That is, instructional decisions for the whole class and provisions to meet their needs can be made easily through the use of varied information regarding the learner. One of the major purposes of Mathematics instruction is to arouse and develop among students the appreciation for the subject. This includes knowledge, skills and attitudes to equip the students with mathematical concepts and principles and values that are expected to be acquired during the teaching – learning situations.

Although studies of teachers' mathematical knowledge have not demonstrated a strong relationship between teachers' mathematical knowledge and their students' achievement, teachers' knowledge is still likely a significant factor in students' achievement. That crude of measures of teacher knowledge, such as the number of mathematics courses taken, do not correlate positively with student performance data, and supports the need to study more closely the nature of the mathematical knowledge needed to be taught and to measure it more sensitively.

Mathematics anxiety results in poor performance rather than the reverse. From the International Mathematics Olympiad, details showed

that the Philippines ranked 79th out of 82 countries in 2003 and 80th out of 85 countries in 2004. Based on the possible maximum points of 225, China got the highest score of 220 points, Vietnam 126, Thailand 9, and the Philippines 16 points (DepEd, 2003). It is alarming that Filipinos are found lacking in the ability of basic mathematics. Research studies being done regarding the basic mathematical knowledge of teachers show their deficiency.

The goal of education is to help students learn how to think effectively and productively. Thinking as the care of learning is at the heart of education. When one thinks, the purpose is to solve problems, make decisions, understand things and concepts, search for answers to questions, look for meanings and make sense of things and situations. Within the context of the aforementioned premises, authorities in the educational system never stop devising, experimenting, and trying out approaches for learning. There is a never – ending flow of revisions and redirections introduced in the schools and in the world of work.

This researcher has been teaching Mathematics in the elementary level; he has continuously experienced some difficulties. These difficulties of the researcher in the delivery of instruction are in part, a result of findings of the low readiness level of pupils. This is validated by other colleagues in the same school, as well as in other schools in the Division of Pangasinan II. Conformably, the researcher learned through conferences, and continuously read in the periodicals about the deterioration of the quality of education in the country. Survey also shows that the secondary school students are not prepared to enter their level, and the former Secretary of Education Edilberto de Jesus designed the “bridging program” which was unpopular to the people (Philippine Star, 2004). Lastly, the International Mathematics and Science tests results showed that the Philippines is near the lowest end of the ranking among participating nations.

Mistretta (2004) found out in his study that students’ confidence in solving and analyzing problems in Mathematics, their interest, enjoyment, and their disposition toward mathematics is influenced by learning environment they encounter. Attitudes were found to be shaped in great part by the learning environments one experiences like their teacher and the classroom atmosphere. Bete (2005) investigated the relationship of mathematics achievement of the fourth year high school students to their general scholastic ability, attitude toward mathematics and educational aspirations. The investigation revealed a significant and positive relationship between students’ mathematical achievement and their general scholastic ability with the effect of their attitude toward mathematics and educational aspirations.

Fortea (2007) in her study of factors contributing to the attitude of the college students toward mathematics are brought by the combined influences emanating from the students themselves, the mathematics teachers and the environment. The negative and the positive attitude of the students toward mathematics are caused by the students’ belief and he concepts about the subjects, skills and the competence of the teacher, family, and the peer influence.

Moreover, there is a need therefore to measure the degree of achievement of mathematical process skills of Grade 6 learners in order to know what skills are to be strengthened. The results of this study are valuable to mathematics teachers and school administrators. The data can provide baseline information for the improvement of mathematics instruction in the elementary schools. This will greatly help concerned people in the academe. It will become the key to realize the achievement of quality education. It is in line with the aforementioned situation that this researcher decided to assess the Mathematical word problem solving and attitude toward mathematics of the learners.

Research Questions

This study focused on the performance level and attitude toward Mathematics of the learners in Jimmy Carter Middle School, Albuquerque Public Schools during the school year 2021-2022 as basis for motivational strategies in the new normal to improve the performance of the learners. Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the Mathematics teachers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.2 length of service; and
 - 1.3 relevant trainings attended?
2. What is the performance level of the learners during first quarter?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and their performance in Mathematics?
4. What is the extent of learners’ attitude in learning Mathematics along the following concerns:
 - 4.1 school – related factors;
 - 4.1.1 study habits; and
 - 4.1.2 peers?
 - 4.2 family – related factors; and
 - 4.2.1 parents; and
 - 4.2.2 siblings?
 - 4.3 teacher – related factor?
 - 4.3.1 teaching method?
5. Based on the findings, what motivational strategies in the new normal can be proposed in teaching Mathematics?

Methodology

This section discussed the research design, sources of data, instrumentation and data collection and the tools for data analysis.

Research Design

The study used descriptive-developmental method with questionnaire as the research instrument. Descriptive research method obtains facts about existing conditions or significant relationship between current phenomena. Developmental because it developed problem-solving instructional materials in Mathematics for the learners.

This study focused on the performance level and attitude toward Mathematics of the learners in Jimmy Carter Middle School, Albuquerque Public Schools as basis for motivational strategies in the new normal to improve the performance of the learners. It looked into the profile of the Mathematics teachers; performance level of the learners during first quarter; significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and their performance in Mathematics; learners' attitude in learning Mathematics.

Participants

The respondents of this study were the Mathematics teachers and learners of Jimmy Carter Middle School, Albuquerque Public Schools during the school year 2021-2022.

Instruments

The main data-gathering instrument of the study was a questionnaire checklist. The questionnaire was formulated by the researcher and was validated by the Mathematics Supervisor and teachers. Suggestions were incorporated in the final draft of the test.

A formal permission to conduct the study and to float the questionnaire was secured from the principal of Jimmy Carter Middle School, Albuquerque Public Schools during the school year 2021-2022. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents in each section and immediately checked the papers in order to get the least learned skills.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered relative to sub-problems in the study.

Profile of the Mathematics Teachers

The profile of the Mathematics Teachers in terms of highest educational attainment, number of years of experience in teaching; and relevant in-service trainings attended is presented in Tables 1A-1C.

Table 1.1 *Profile of the Mathematics Teachers in Terms of Highest Educational Attainment (N=18)*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
With MA Units	12	66.67
MAEd/Med	6	33.33
Total	18	100

It can be gleaned in Table 1A that a great number of the Mathematics teachers have MA units with 12 or 66.67%. Some 6 or 33.33% are MAEd or MEd graduates. It could be observed from the data that there are more teachers who are pursuing graduate studies because of the increase in salary that goes alongside with the promotion as teachers, a good number of them subscribe to the importance of professional growth. It can also be noted that some of them are graduate of masteral degree because they are aiming for higher position like being school head or Master Teachers.

Table 1.2 *Profile of the Mathematics Teachers in Terms of Number of Years of Experience in Teaching (N=18)*

<i>Length of Teaching Experience</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
0-5 years	6	33.33
6-10 years	8	45.45
11-15 years	4	22.22
Total	18	100

It is reflected in Table 1B that most of the Mathematics teachers have been teaching or 6-10 years with 8 or 45.45%. This is followed by 0-5 with 6 or 33.33% and 11-15 years with 4 or 22.22%. The result shows that the teacher-respondents have average length of service.

Table 1.3 *Profile of the Mathematics Teachers Terms of Relevant Trainings Attended*

<i>Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Division	18	100
Regional	9	50

*Multiple Responses

It is shown in Table 1C that all Mathematics teachers had attended Division trainings. On the other hand, 9 or 50% of them had attended Regional trainings. The results show that Mathematics teachers give importance to trainings or seminars because of the belief that experience is the best teachers. Through seminars, they can improve their competencies and skills in teaching.

Performance Level of Learners during First Quarter

The performance level of the learners in terms of academic rating during fourth quarter is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. *Performance Rating during First Quarter (N=135)*

Academic Rating during Third Quarter	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding (90 and above)	48	35.56
Very Satisfactory (85-89)	54	40.00
Satisfactory (80-84)	20	14.81
Fair (75-79)	13	9.63
Total	135	100

It can be seen in Table 2 that majority of the learners obtained a performance rating of Very Satisfactory with 54 or 40%. There are also 48 or 35.56% who got an Outstanding Performance. Some of the received a Satisfactory performance with 20 or 14.81%. The remaining 13 or 9.63% got a Fair rating.

The result supports the study of Ledda (2006) when she claimed that lack of instructional materials contributes to the low performance of the pupils. Many of the learners are deficient with their knowledge of Mathematics. It is indeed an observation that lack of instructional material could be one of the reasons why pupils are not performing well in the class, not gaining attention and not motivated to learn and participate in every classroom activity.

Relationship Between the Profile of Teachers and the Level of Performance of the Learners

Table 3. *Correlation between the Profile of Teachers and the Level of Performance of the Learners*

Profile of Teachers	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (p)	Interpretation	Correlation Interpretation
Highest Educational Attainment	.211	.002	Significant	Low Correlation
Length of Service	.214	.001	Significant	Low Correlation
Relevant Trainings Attended	.181	.001	Significant	Low Correlation
Overall Score	.221	.001	Significant	Low Correlation

The results revealed that statistically, profile of teachers and the level of performance of the learners ($r=.221$) had low correlation. The p-value 0.001 would suggest that, overall, correlations made are highly significant which gives probability of error less than 1% (i.e. 0.1%) in the null hypothesis.

It concludes that statistically, there is no enough evidence to say that there is a significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and the level of performance of the Grade 5 learners during the third quarter examination. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted since the statistics reveals that the correlations made were under the range of low correlation to negligible correlation. This is also consistent with the p-values computed that out of four competencies, three are considered to be significant either at 0.01 or 0.05 level. This implies that it exceeds the value of probability to be considered in order to determine that the null hypothesis made is true.

Learners' Attitude in Learning Mathematics

The learners' attitude in learning Mathematics in terms of school-related factors, family-related factors, and teacher-related factors is shown in Table 4A-4C.

It is clearly shown in Table 4A that learners' attitude in learning Mathematics in terms of practice/habits is moderate extent as reflected by the average weighted mean of 3.22.

A. School - Related Factors

Table 4.1 *Learners' Attitude in Learning Mathematics in Terms of Practice/Habits (N=18)*

Practice / Habits	WM	DE
1. Studies Math lessons daily because it is a must.	3.50	ME
2. Studies Math only if there are assignments.	3.24	ME
3. Studies Math only when there is a quiz / test scheduled.	3.06	ME
4. Studies Math only when told by parents.	3.25	ME
5. Studies Math only when told by teachers.	3.01	ME
6. Studies Math only when told by friends, classmates, and peers.	3.22	ME
7. Studies Math only when seen others studying the subject	3.09	ME
8. Studies Math because they like the subject.	3.14	ME
9. Studies Math because they like the teacher.	3.54	ME
10. Studies Math only when there is no work to do at home.	3.12	ME
AWM	3.22	ME

4.21 – 5.00 High Extent; 3.41 – 4.20 Extent; 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent; 1.81 – 2.60 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.80 Very Low Extent

The indicator “Studies Math because they like the teacher” got the highest mean rating of 3.54 while the lowest mean rating of 3.01 was given to the indicator “Studies Math only when told by friends, classmates, and peers” though both were described as moderately extent. The result shows that teachers need to encourage the learners to improve their attitude towards Mathematics so that their performance will also improve.

Table 4.2 Learners’ Attitude in Learning Mathematics in Terms of Peer Influence (N=18)

Peer Influence	WM	DE
1. Joining classmates for a group work in Math.	3.16	ME
2. Joining classmates who cut classes especially during Math periods because it is difficult and boring.	2.54	LE
3. Going with classmates who do not mind Math subjects because the teacher is unlikable.	3.12	ME
4. Joining friends do assignment.	2.76	ME
5. Prefer going with friends and classmates than attending Math period because I feel sleepy listening to lecture.	3.35	ME
6. Joining friends and classmates who can teach me solve exercises and problems.	2.99	ME
AWM	2.99	ME

4.21 – 5.00 High Extent; 3.41 – 4.20 Extent; 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent; 1.81 – 2.60 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.80 Very Low Extent

In terms of peer influence, a 2.99 average weighed mean was generated which is described as moderate extent. The indicator “Prefer going with friends and classmates than attending Math period because I feel sleepy listening to lecture” got he highest mean of 3.35 which means that learners are disinterested in learning Mathematics because of the influence of peers and sometimes due to teacher’s strategy in teaching the lesson. On the other hand, the indicator “Joining classmates who cut classes especially during Math periods because it is difficult and boring” received a weighted mean of 2.54 which is also described as low extent.

B. Family – Related Factors

In terms of family- related factors such as parents, learners’ attitude in learning Mathematics obtained an average weighed mean of 3.21 which is described as moderate extent. The indicator “The parents praise good work and high grades achieved by the pupils in Mathematics” received the highest mean of 3.32 while the lowest mean rating of 3.14 was given to the indicator “The parents of the pupils give them enough time to study their lessons”. The result shows that parents moderately influence their sons/daughters to study Mathematics harder.

Table 5.1 Learners’ Attitude in Learning Mathematics in Terms of Parents (N=18)

Parents	WM	DE
1. The parents of the learners encourage them to devote more time to study Mathematics very well.	3.23	ME
2. The parents of the pupils give them enough time to study their lessons.	3.14	ME
3. The parents of the learners do not disturb them when they are studying.	3.17	ME
4. The parents of the learners discuss assignment in Mathematics with me them.	3.19	ME
5. The parents praise good work and high grades achieved by the learners in Mathematics.	3.32	ME
	3.21	ME

4.21 – 5.00 High Extent; 3.41 – 4.20 Extent; 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent; 1.81 – 2.60 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.80 Very Low Extent

The Grade 5 learners’ attitude in learning Mathematics in terms of siblings got an average weighed mean of 3.24 which is described as moderate extent. The highest mean rating was given to the indicator “The siblings of the learners view television programs / VCD’s about Mathematics with them, with proper assistance and guidance” with 3.43 which is described as “extent”. On the other hand, the lowest mean rating of 3.12 was given to the indicator “The siblings of the learners give them Mathematics book as gift.” The result shows that the learners’ siblings influence them moderately in learning Mathematics.

Table 5.2 Learners’ Attitude in Learning Mathematics in Terms of Siblings (N=18)

Siblings	WM	DE
1. The siblings of the learners give them Mathematics book as gift.	3.12	ME
2. The siblings of the learner’s view television programs / VCD’s about Mathematics with them, with proper assistance and guidance.	3.43	E
3. The siblings of the learners check them if they prepare their things and other materials in Mathematics before going to school.	3.18	ME
4. The siblings of the learners help them to do their assignments regularly especially in Mathematics.	3.14	ME
5. The siblings of the learners check the answers to their assigned Mathematics problems / concepts	3.35	ME
	3.24	ME

4.21 – 5.00 High Extent; 3.41 – 4.20 Extent; 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent; 1.81 – 2.60 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.80 Very Low Extent

C. Teacher – Related Factors

Table 6. Learners’ Attitude in Learning Mathematics in Terms of Teaching Method / Strategy (N=18)

Teaching Method / Strategy	WM	DE
1. Uses the chalk and board in lecturing.	3.45	E
2. Explains the lesson before giving exercises to learners.	3.41	E

3. Gives exercises to students before explaining the lesson.	3.54	E
4. In problem - solving, explains the procedures / steps, then solve the problem and after which let the learners solve similar problems.	3.61	E
5. Presents a solved problem and requires the learners discover the procedures or steps in solving the problem.	3.31	ME
AWM	3.46	E

4.21 – 5.00 High Extent; 3.41 – 4.20 Extent; 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent; 1.81 – 2.60 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.80 Very Low Extent

In terms of the learners' attitude in learning Mathematics along teaching method/strategy of teachers, it obtained an average weighted mean of 3.46 which is described as "extent". The highest mean rating of 3.61 was given to the indicator "In problem - solving, explains the procedures / steps, then solve the problem and after which let the learners solve similar problems." The lowest mean rating on the other hand was given to 3.31 which is considered "moderate extent". The result shows that Mathematics teachers are exerting a lot of effort in order to teachers the learners well. They possessed positive attitude towards the learners and towards the subject.

Conclusion

In the course of the findings of this study, the following conclusions are formulated: (1) Generally, most of the Mathematics teachers are educationally qualified, with minimum teaching experience, and attended various seminars about Mathematics. (2) The learners obtained a very satisfactory performance. (3) The profile of the teachers is significantly related to the level of performance of the learners in Mathematics. (4) The attitude of the learners towards Mathematics along School – related factors such as Study habits and Peers; Family – related factors like Parents; and Siblings; and Teacher – related factor are the factors affecting the performance of the learners. (5) The proposed motivational strategies could improve the attitude and performance of learners towards Mathematics.

On the basis of the foregoing findings and conclusions, the following are recommended: (1) The proposed motivational strategies should be presented to the Schools Division Superintendent for its reproduction and utilization to help the Mathematics teachers. (2) Teachers should make instructional materials to improve the performance of the pupils. Such intervention/materials help them understand more clearly the concepts. (3) Parents and teachers should join hands in improving the performance of the students. Teachers should tell the parents about the difficulties encountered by their children in learning Mathematics. Parents should also monitor the performance of their children in the school. They should give their full support in their studies like attending PTA meetings and have follow-ups in their studies. (4) The least learned skills in Mathematics should be given emphasis in teaching. Teachers should use appropriate strategy and techniques to develop the skills and give more exercise for the students to master the skills.

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